
EFFECTS OF AQUEOUS EXTRACTS OF *Rauvolfia vomitoria* and *Citrus aurantium* ON LIVER ENZYMES OF STREPTOZOTOCIN – INDUCED DIABETIC AND NORMAL RABBITS.

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ABSTRACT

In the search for a potential cure for Diabetes, a chronic and potentially debilitating disease when poorly managed, the need for a lasting biochemically friendly cure is pertinent. Phytochemicals have long been highly recommended in the safe management of various ailments, especially chronic diseases. This study aims at examining the safety of the combined use of aqueous extracts of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* and *Citrus aurantium* fruit in the treatment of streptozotocin-induced diabetes in rabbits at different dosages. Its oral administration produced a significant hypoglycaemic effect ($P < 0.05$), without any significant increase ($P > 0.05$) in the serum levels of the liver enzymes glutamic pyruvic transaminase, glutamic oxaloacetate transaminase and lactate dehydrogenase at a dose of 400mg/kg body weight and 800mg/kg body weight administered to induced diabetic and non-diabetic rabbits respectively, using ANOVA. These findings prove the effectiveness of this combination of aqueous plant extracts in lowering blood glucose levels without significant toxic effects on the liver of the English rabbit.

KEYWORDS: Effects, Aqueous extract, *Rauvolfia vomitoria*, *Citrus aurantium*, Liver Enzymes, Diabetic, Normal, Rabbits

INTRODUCTION

Citrus aurantium, belonging to the family Rutaceae is also called sour or bitter orange. The sour orange juice is antiseptic, anti-bilious and hemostatic. Africans apply the cut-open orange on ulcers and yaws and areas of the body afflicted with rheumatism. In Italy, Mexico and Latin America generally, decoctions of the leaves are given for their sudorific, antispasmodic, stimulant, tonic and stomachic action. The flowers, prepared as a syrup, act as a sedative in nervous disorders and induce sleep. An infusion of the bitter bark is taken as a tonic, stimulant, febrifuge and vermifuge. *Rauvolfia vomitoria*, belonging to the family Apocynaceae, is a shrub or small tree growing up to 8 metres, the epithet *vomitoria* referring to the purgative and emetic properties of the bark.

It occurs naturally in gallery forests but is mostly found in forest re-growth where fallow periods are prolonged.

It is widely distributed in Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ghana, Liberia, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan and Uganda. The members of this family usually have toxic properties. The root bark extracts are reportedly poisonous. In Gabon, the bark and root powder, are mixed with water or palm oil to kill fleas and vermin. This tree is however used medicinally in many African countries for example, it is being used by Nigerian traditional healers to treat psychiatric patients. *R. vomitoria* is used to treat leprosy in the Democratic Republic of Congo. The seed extract is procured for general illness. Amyrin palmitate, present in a Ghanaian antiarthritic herbal preparation with *R. vomitoria* has curative properties. The bark has purgative and emetic properties. The root extracts have abortifacient properties. Other products: Two indole alkaloids, 3-epi-rescinnamine and 3,4-dimethoxybenzoyl-reserpine acid methyl ester, are isolated from the root bark of *R. vomitoria*.

Diagnostic enzymology is the use of enzymes in diagnosing (or differentiating between) certain or specific diseases. When enzymes are present in the blood, they are usually in small concentration. But when there is damage to an organ, the enzyme present in the organ leaks out into the blood. The enzyme glutamic pyruvic transaminase (GPT) is prevalent in mammalian tissues, it catalyses the transfer of the amino group of alanine to α -ketoglutarate (Stryer, 1995). GPT is a cytosol enzyme, more specific to the liver so that a rise only occurs

with liver disease (Kumar and Clark, 2001). Its levels are tested to look for and evaluate damage to the liver. It is also measured to check medical treatments that may lead to liver inflammation. Glutamic oxaloacetate transaminase (GOT) is also specific to the liver and indicates derangement in liver metabolism.

Lactate dehydrogenase is an enzyme that catalyses the reduction of pyruvate by NADH to form lactate. The reaction occurs in cells of higher organisms when the amount of oxygen is limiting (hypoxic condition) as in muscle during intense activity (Stryer, 1995).

Lactate dehydrogenase is present in almost all body tissues, so the LDH test is used to detect tissues alterations and as an aid in the diagnosis of heart attack, anemia, and liver disease (David *et al.*, 2000). When disease or injury affects tissues containing LDH, the cells release LDH into the blood stream, where it is identified in higher than normal levels. For example, when a person has a heart attack, the LDH levels begin to rise about 2 hours after attack and usually returns to normal within 5-10days. The LDH is also elevated in diseases of the liver, certain types of anaemia, and in cases of excessive destruction of cells, such as fractures, trauma, muscle damage and shock (David *et al.*, 2000).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

Latex disposable gloves, syringes and needles, fluoride oxalate bottles, plain sterile bottles, test tubes, test tube racks, blood samples, transfer pipette, micropipettes, incubator, centrifuge (80-2 B-bran), water bath (B-bran) spectrophotometer (Spectrum lab 722s), cuvette (1cm light path), picric acid, electric hot plate, crucibles, mouse gavage.

Reagents and kits required include Glutamic-pyruvate transaminase (GPT), Glutamic Oxaloacetate Transaminase (GOT) and lactate dehydrogenase kits, all from Randox laboratories (California U.S.A). Citrate buffer, sodium hydroxide and deionised water.

Test Subject

Twenty-four-month old English rabbits (males and females) obtained from animal unit of Pharmacy Department University of Benin, Benin City. The Rabbits were kept in standard cages in the laboratory and fed on grower's mash throughout the duration of the research work.

They were divided into 4 groups of 5 rabbits each, supplied with water in standard cans and allowed to acclimatize for one month before commencement of the research. The weight of these rabbits ranged between 1.1 – 1.9kg.

Preparation of Plant Extract

The leaves attached to young stems of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* were plucked off the stem, washed and weighed, (2kg) and combined with quartered whole citrus fruits (total weight, 4.5kg) arranged in alternate layers and placed in a large aluminium pot. The plant material was then covered with 10L of tap water, brought to boil and allowed to simmer covered at low heat for three hours. The resulting brownish coloured fluid was cooled to room temperature and filtered through coarse filters. The total yield of extract was about 4.5L and was subsequently stored at -4°C throughout the whole duration of the research.

To determine the quantity of active principle 10ml of extract was evaporated to dryness and the weight of dried residue (active principle) was 1.125g; hence 1ml of the extract will contain 0.1125g of active principle. The rabbits in groups 1 and 3 were treated with 400mg/kg and 800mg/kg of the extract respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL INDUCTION OF DIABETES IN RABBITS

Diabetes was induced by streptozotocin (STZ) sigma, at a dose of 65mg/kg administered intraperitoneally (I.P) in physiologic saline with pH adjusted to 4.5 using citric acid (i.e. 0.05M citrate buffer) as described by Palanichamy *et al.*, (1998).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The rabbits were divided into 4 groups of five (5) groups of animals in each group. The RVCA extract was fed to the rabbits by gavage.

Group 1: Diabetic rats treated with *Rauvolfia vomitoria* and *Citrus aurantium* (RVCA) extract (Test).

Group 2: Induced diabetic (Test control) rabbits not treated with RVCA extract.

Group 3: Not induced but treated with double dose of RVCA extract,

Group 4: Normal Control

Animals in group 1 were fed RVCA extract at a dose of 400mg/kg body weight per day while groups 3 were fed at a dose of 800mg/kg body weight per day. Baseline values were taken for fasting blood sugar, Lactate dehydrogenase, Glutamic-pyruvic and Glutamic oxaloacetate transaminase assays and body weight.

At one and four weeks post-treatment these parameters were again assayed. Blood for all assays was collected from the marginal ear vein into fluoride oxalate (for blood sugar) and plain sterile bottles immersed in ice for liver enzyme assay. The tubes were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain clear plasma (fluoride oxalate) and serum (plain sterile bottles). The plasma and serum were then separated from the blood cells and analysis for blood glucose, lactate dehydrogenase, Glutamic-pyruvate transaminase and Glutamic-oxaloacetate transaminase in accordance with the Randox test kits obtained from California

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The values of results were estimated as mean and standard error of mean (SEM) and tests of significance done using INSTAT statistical software.

RESULTS

The results of the assay of the liver enzymes are as presented in the tables.

TABLE 1: SERUM LACTATE DEHYDROGENASE LEVELS

GROUPS	Baseline (Mean \pm S.E.M)	1 st wk Post treatment (Mean \pm S.E.M)	4wks Post treatment (Mean \pm S.E.M)
GROUP 1	222.63 \pm 27.40	168.87 \pm 3.37	263.91 \pm 63.49
GROUP 2	176.28 \pm 32.30	186.71 \pm 9.954	198.82 \pm 32.58
GROUP 3	180.08 \pm 25.110	169.50 \pm 12.552	96.26 \pm 46.01
GROUP 4	186.00 \pm 0.00	162.50 \pm 0.00	114.71 \pm 0.00

TABLE 2: SERUM GLUTAMIC-PYRUVIC TRANSAMINASE LEVELS

GROUPS	Baseline (Mean \pm S.E.M)	1 st wk Post treatment (Mean \pm S.E.M)	4wks Post treatment (Mean \pm S.E.M)
GROUP 1	9.33 \pm 0.67	9.77 \pm 1.49	19.33 \pm 1.45
GROUP 2	8.00 \pm 0.15	7.60 \pm 0.40	29.00 \pm 7.77
GROUP 3	9.17 \pm 1.167	8.67 \pm 0.67	27.33 \pm 0.33
GROUP 4	6.80 \pm 1.02	5.00 \pm 0.34	17.00 \pm 2.43

TABLE 3: SERUM GLUTAMIC-OXALO TRANSAMINASE LEVELS

GROUPS	Baseline (Mean \pm S.E.M)	1 st wk Post treatment (Mean \pm S.E.M)	4wks Post treatment (Mean \pm S.E.M)
GROUP 1	7.56 \pm 1.34	11.23 \pm 1.21	18.31 \pm 0.12
GROUP 2	13.21 \pm 0.43	15.12 \pm 0.56	21.33 \pm 0.97
GROUP 3	10.45 \pm 0.23	13.65 \pm 1.34	19.33 \pm 1.23
GROUP 4	7.67 \pm 1.12	11.05 \pm 1.22	16.43 \pm 0.47

TABLE 4: EFFECTS OF RVCA EXTRACT ON BLOOD GLUCOSE, SERUM GLUTAMIC-PYRUVIC TRANSAMINASE (SGPT), SERUM GLUTAMIC-OXALO TRANSAMINASE (SGOT) AND LACTATE DEHYDROGENASE IN STZ-DIABETES INDUCED RABBITS, COMPARED WITH NORMAL CONTROL AND NORMAL TREATED RABBITS FOUR WEEKS POST TREATMENT

Serum assay	Group 4	Group 2	Group 3
Glucose	76.64 ± 0.00	424.825	78.50 ± 43
GPT	17.00 ± 0.00	29.00 ± 7.77	19.33 ± 1.45
LDH	114.71 ± 0.00	198.82 ± 32.58	236.91 ± 63.49
GOT	16.43 ± 0.47	21.33 ± 0.97	19.33 ± 1.23

TABLE 5: LIVER BODY WEIGHT RATIO AT FOUR WEEKS POST TREATMENT.

Test Group	Liver Weight(g)	Body Weight(g)	Liver: Body Weight ratio
Group 1	27.06	1170	1:43
Group 2	24.5	1800	1:73
Group 3	32.5	1460	1:45
Group 4	31.3	1400	1:44

DISCUSSION

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycaemia resulting from a defect in insulin secretion, insulin action or both. This therefore leads to an elevation in the blood glucose levels and a stimulation of an alternate pathway and mobilization of lipid stores, to provide energy for the body's needed metabolisms. These events can be detected and monitored by various chemical tests of the urine and blood. (Guyton and Hall, 1996).

Likewise, traditional herbal treatments are used in Nigeria to treat various ailments e.g. diabetes mellitus, sickle cell anaemia. This indigenous form of medicine uses active ingredients present in plants for treating disease. Plant products are frequently considered to be less toxic and more free from side effects than synthetic ones. (Pari and Uma, 1999).

Citrus aurantium and *Rauvolfia vomitoria* are the plants used in this study. They were both administered to the experimental animals in a mixed aqueous extract and fed to both STZ-induced diabetic and normal rabbits to treat the resulting elevated blood glucose (hyperglycaemia) and hyperlipidaemia found prevalent in diabetes mellitus. The study aimed at determining the toxic effects of the extract on the liver. The statistical analysis was done using the InStat software. This provided the analysis of variation for the various comparisons using the Kruskal-Wallis statistics, Dunn's multiple comparisons test, T-test, Mean and Standard error of mean. These results are also discussed from close relative scientific observations made during the study.

Rabbits induced with streptozotocin that were treated with 400mg/kg body weight of RVCA extract were found to have increased serum levels of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) (Table 1) and Glutamic-pyruvic transaminase (GPT) (Fig Table 2), Glutamic oxalo transaminase (Table 3) at four weeks post treatment with respect to their baseline value. However, this difference was not statistically significant and may not be attributed to the effects of the extract on the liver because there was also an increase in the serum values of Lactate dehydrogenase, Glutamic-pyruvic transaminase and Glutamic oxalo transaminase of normal treated rabbits and the difference was also not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Also at 800mg/kg body weight dose of RVCA extract, there was an increase in the serum values of Lactate dehydrogenase, Glutamic pyruvic transaminase and Glutamic oxalo- transaminase, but these were not statistically significant

After four weeks of treatment with the extract, the liver body weight ratio of the experimental rabbits ranged between 1:43 to 1:73. STZ- induced and normal treated rabbits showed no statistically significant change ($p > 0.05$) when compared with the normal control group showing no adverse effect of the RVCA extract on the liver of either STZ-induced rabbits treated with 400mg/kg body weight dose of extract nor the normal rabbits treated with double the concentration of extract. (Table 5)

The pharmacological activity of this extract i.e the active principle and its mechanism of action is not totally known but it has been discovered that *Citrus aurantium* aqueous extract is an inhibitor of cytochrome P450(CYP) 3A4 enzyme thereby potentiating the effects of drugs which are metabolized by the cytochrome P450 isozyme (Guyton and Hall (1996)).

There is evidence from this study that *Citrus aurantium* and *Rauvolfia vomitoria* can be used in the long term treatment of diabetes mellitus, with minimal potential for toxicity considering that serum Lactate dehydrogenase, serum Glutamic pyruvate transaminase and serum Glutamic oxalo transaminase are maintained within normal range during its use. This indicates the relative non-toxicity of the aqueous extract of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* and *Citrus aurantium* on the liver.

It is therefore recommended that further studies on the active principle and dosage form be conducted to fine tune its pharmacologic and pharmaceutical uses.

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